

Impact of Logistic Collaboration on Supply Chain Performance

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Abstract

This quantitative study aims to identify the impact of logistic collaboration on supply chain performance. For this purpose, the influence of the characteristics involving trust, organizational commitment, interdependence of supply chain, involvement of information technology and involvement of top management were explored. The results indicate that all of the characteristics of supply chain collaboration have a significant positive impact on supply chain performance except the factor of trust among supply chain partners. The study recommends supply chain collaboration as an important element for increasing supply chain performance. The study opens directions for future studies in the area of supply chain collaboration.

Keywords: Supply chain performance, Supply chain collaboration, Trust, Organizational commitment, Interdependence of supply chain.

Introduction

Supply chain is a growing area in logistic management. The modern concepts of supply chain management have increased flexibility and economic efficiency of logistics (Yusuf et al., 2022). Integrated planning in supply chain management does not only help in effective decision making but it has built the foundation of highly efficient supply chain. Supply chain management is regarded as the universal model for doing business which is based on the principles and capabilities of information technology (Zhou & Li, 2020). Logistic collaboration is a key factor in supply chain for improving the overall productivity, competitiveness, and business efficiency of logistics and trading companies. It is attained when one or more organizations work together for achieving production efficiency which is difficult to achieve for the any organization when it is working alone. Logistic collaboration integrates objectives and strategies of organizations which is crucial for maintaining competitive advantage. Organizations collaborate by pooling the resources of their customers and supply partners. Collaboration aims to enhance the efficiency and responsiveness by minimizing obstacles (Mahmud et al., 2021). The benefits of collaboration for business enterprises have been reported in several researches. It has also been reported the challenges faced in logistics collaboration stems from a variety of issues, including incompatible technology, a lack of competent staff, and poor networking with key supply chain partners. Organizational commitment, trust, interdependence of supply chain members, involvement of technology and top management are the areas of concerns which needs to be highlighted for sustaining logistic collaboration (Jami et al., 2022).

Hou et al. (2018) describes significance of trust in enabling logistic alliance. According to him mistrust among organizational partners, disrupted relationships, differences in goals, mis commitment can produce a lack of information sharing and investment of assets. Mistrust can greatly impact flexibility against interruptions in supply chain. Paul et al. (2016) explains that joint performance of supply chain decreases due to mis commitment. Organizational commitment demands that all partners of the supply chain must be committed to achieve common goals which in turn create productivity.

It has also been explained that maintaining reciprocal interdependencies of supply chain partners is not easy. Supply chain partners should identify ways of communicating and conveying information to build coordination in supply chain activities. Moreover, logistic collaboration and information technology are identified as direct enablers of product innovation, with information technology as the motivator for supply chain collaboration. Information technology is directly related to product innovation in supply chain. Ma et al., (2020) stated that top managerial support is an important enabler of logistic collaboration as the top managerial support is crucial for decision making and managing finances. Top management support has

been regarded as the strongest enabler who indicates the motivation to build relationships and connections between buyers, sellers or financial service providers.

Numerous researchers have listed the above-mentioned enablers from various perspectives. However, there is a strong need to define feasible coordination enablers and to investigate how these enablers can be implemented (Chu et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020). Therefore, this research aims to analyse the effect of logistic collaboration on the performance of supply chain industry. The research will examine organizational commitment, trust, and interdependence among supply chain partnership, technology and infrastructure as the factors underlying logistic collaboration and observe its impact on supply chain performance.

The research will directly benefit the business entities in supply chain management by determining the factors, which are effective for creating successful logistic collaboration. It will aid in the development of economic strategies for effective business practices. Moreover, the results will also assist in decision making processes for business development. The study is an attempt to optimize business collaboration inter-organizational based on modern managerial practices. It will suggest the operative practice of implementing supply chain management in modern logistics and has the potential to evolve rapidly in the future.

Literature Review

Supply Chain and Logistics

The concepts of logistics and supply chain are often confused with each other. There are reasons for this identification with each other, because they are sets of activities that are connected and are dependent on each other (Durach et al., 2021). Logistics refers to the processes related to planning the distribution, storage and circulation of products. The main idea of logistics is to deliver the products to the customer in the shortest possible time and at the lowest cost. Resources are developed and used to understand traffic routes, storage locations, means of transportation for this purpose (Richey et al., 2022).

Logistics is also responsible for controlling the flow of goods in an efficient and effective way, from the origin to the consumption. The main purpose of logistics is to meet the customers' demands. Supplies are processed, managed, stored and transported through logistics (Golpîra et al., 2022). The concept of logistic is also important to emphasize in supply chain which refers to the methods used in order to obtain better management and integration of different parameters. When all these concepts are united, there is a strategic management of the different flows and relationships between companies in order to achieve organizational goals (Richey et al., 2022).

The core benefit that efficient supply chain management will provide is the reduction of inventories. Keeping them lower and lower is an effective way to reduce logistical costs, but it needs to be done safely and planned. To be truly satisfying, logistics supply chain management relies heavily on state-of-the-art technology, represented mainly by software that helps to optimize relationships and processes (Durach et al., 2021). For example, in the case of suppliers, it is possible to install an extranet system or even a basic barcode system to optimize the period between the input request (raw material, finished product, semi-finished product) and its delivery. With an automated system integrated between company and supplier, the latter will always be aware of the needs of its customer, which will help to ensure that the necessary raw materials are never missing (Richey et al., 2022).

Logistic Collaboration

As the name suggests, it addresses collaboration between business partners - suppliers, distributors, service providers, and others - and even customers, in order to optimize processes and bring savings to the operation (Zhou et al., 2022). In such cases, instead of acting alone in the market, all players come together and contribute strategic information about the market and the best practices in the logistics sector. This creates a solid chain of collaboration, improving service delivery, increasing capacity, and strengthening all the companies involved - which are competing as a stronger and stronger group (Badraoui et al., 2022).

The technical definition of this term is consistent with the coordinated activities of shippers and carriers in order to achieve improvements in both profitability and business performance as a whole (Richey et al., 2022). Among the direct and indirect agents of the supply chain are raw materials, machinery, finished products and all kinds of logistic information. This chain is broad, and it is a network made up of suppliers, manufacturers, distributors and consumers (Badraoui et al., 2022).

The compression of relations between supply chain participants in recent decades has influenced a renewal in the traditional way of transporting loads between any distances. Similarly, recent advances in the technological field have dictated the rules of a new market, more flexible and fuller of opportunities. In this context, new corporate relationships emerged based on trust and collaboration between the parties, with a view to the sustainability of the operations of the companies involved (Shcherbakov et al., 2021). Through logistics collaboration, businesses of all sizes were encouraged to join forces to optimize their logistics processes and reduce costs in this area (Susanto et al., 2021).

Methodology

The researcher used the quantitative research paradigm, which is appropriate for most marketing and business studies. To investigate the research variables, the researcher developed a questionnaire from many writers (Mafini & Loury-Okoumba, 2015; Niu, 2010; Sundaram & Pandiyan, 2012). The researcher created a questionnaire to assess the influence of independent variables on dependent variable. The questionnaire was based on Likert scale from 1 to 5 where 1 is lowest level of agreement and 5 is the highest level of agreement. The demographic information through the questionnaire was regarding the gender and the name of the company. There were six constructs in the questionnaire. The first construct was for measuring variable “trust among supply chain partners” which included 6 items for example “we generally trust our suppliers to follow code of conduct”. The second construct was for variable organizational commitment including 5 items for example “we pay our suppliers on time”. The fourth construct was made for variable “interdependence of supply chain members with 7 items for example “our suppliers’ deliver products on time”. Fifth construct of the questionnaire was regarding integration of “supply chain information and technology which composed of 6 items for example “our suppliers depend on our business for achieving their goals”. Sixth construct was for “top managerial involvement including 5 items for example “Thinks of bottom-up approach”. The last construct defines dependent variable supply chain performance with 5 items for example “ability to respond to and accommodate demand”. There were 34 items in the questionnaire with six constructs.

Following data collection, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyse the data set. Descriptive data were acquired to determine the number of respondents, their age, and gender. Means and standard deviations were determined based on gender, birth order, and age difference. The internal consistency of the items was tested at two phases

Findings

The descriptive analysis of the demographic data obtained from the respondents indicates that among total of 300 respondents, 103 were females and 197 respondents were male. The highest number of respondents was belonged to Pepsi Cola industry.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

Gender				
	Freq	Perc	Valid Per	Cumulative Per
Female	103	34.3	34.3	34.3
Male	197	65.6	65.6	100.0
Company				
Gourmet Cola	87	29.0	29.0	29.0
Coca Cola	100	33.3	33.3	33.3
Pepsi	113	37.6	37.6	100.0
Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Reliability & Validity

Table 2 shows the internal consistency of the questions, which was tested in two phases including pilot testing and final testing in order to ensure the tool used to collect data from the survey population was reliable. The internal consistency of the items for each construct was judged to be trustworthy in both pilot

and final testing so the instrument used was deemed reliable for the subsequent step. None of the items were under consideration for removal.

Table 2
Internal Consistency

	Pilot Test	N of Items	Final Test	N of Items
Trust	.867	6	.898	6
Organizational Commitment	.813	5	.850	5
Interdependence of Supply Chain	.848	7	.811	7
Informational Technology	.710	6	.712	6
Top Managerial Involvement	.835	5	.802	5
Supply Chain Performance	.705	5	.717	5

Table 3 displays the results for KMO and Bartlett’s test which is used in the study to determine the sampling adequacy.

Table 3
KMO and Bartlett’s Test

KMO test for Sampling Adequacy. .736		
	Approx. Chi-Square	2642.960
Bartlett's Test	df	16
	Sig.	.000

The convergent validity for the constructs in the instrument was tested using Principal Components Analysis (PCA). Table 4 presents the PCA outcome, which demonstrates that 6 constructs were retrieved. The principal component analysis indicates that the constructs used in the study are viable for testing hypothesis.

Table 4
Principal Component Analysis

	Component Matrix					
	Components					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
T1	0.619					
T2	0.535					
T3	0.579					
T4	0.698					
T5	0.719					
T6	0.821					
OC1		0.568				
OC2		0.747				
OC3		0.531				
OC4		0.671				
OC5		0.349				
ISC1			0.651			
ISC2			0.358			
ISC3			0.61			
ISC4			0.717			
ISC5			0.75			
ISC6			0.745			
ISC7			0.602			
IT1				0.604		

IT2	0.697
IT3	0.649
IT4	0.747
IT5	0.531
IT6	0.671
TM1	0.349
TM2	0.697
TM3	0.649
TM4	0.61
TM5	0.717
SC1	0.698
SC2	0.719
SC3	0.821
SC4	0.747
SC5	0.531
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	
6 components extracted.	

The table 5 presents the correlation between the items for the construct used in the study tool.

Table 5
Correlation

		T	OC	ISC	IT	TM	SC
T	Pearson Correlation	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
	N	300					
OC	Pearson Correlation	.744**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000					
	N	300	300				
ISC	Pearson Correlation	.757**	.594**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000				
	N	300	300	306			
IT	Pearson Correlation	.744**	.759**	.864**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000			
	N	300	300	300	300		
TM	Pearson Correlation	.692**	.458**	.881**	.871**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		
	N	300	300	300	300	300	
SC	Pearson Correlation	.766**	.629**	.915**	.720**	.652**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	300	300	300	300	300	300

Inferential Analysis

The predicted hypotheses were tested using backward through SPSS version 22. Table 6 displays the impact of independent variable on the dependent variable. The obtained R-value demonstrates multiple correlation coefficient which suggests that as the change in independent variables (TM, OC, IS, and IT) lead to change in the dependent variable (SCP), whether positively or negatively. The value.872 shows a high level of prediction. The coefficient of determination (.846 = 84.6 percent) is shown by the R Square (R2) value in the second row, which represents the proportion of variation brought by the independent variables (TM, OC, IS, and IT) in the dependent variable.

Table 6

Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.872 ^a	.846	.845	.19001
2	.872 ^b	.846	.845	.18963
a. Predictors: (Constant), TM, OC, T IS, IT				
b. Predictors: (Constant), TM, OC, IS, IT				

Table 7 displays ANOVA analysis that determines the model fitness for regression. The value for F indicates that independent variables top managerial involvement, organizational commitment, interdependence in supply chain and information technology significantly predict supply chain performance. Therefore, it can be said model is fit for regression analysis.

Table 7
ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	194.338	5	38.868	1076.393	.000 ^b
	Residual	10.833	295	.036		
	Total	205.171	300			
2	Regression	194.335	4	48.584	1349.626	.000 ^c
	Residual	10.835	296	.036		
	Total	205.171	300			
a. Dependent Variable: SCP						
b. Predictors: (Constant), TM, OC, T, IS, IT						
c. Predictors: (Constant), TM, OC, IS, IT						

The equation can be represented as

$$\text{Predicted SCP} = -.198 + (.150 \times \text{OC}) + (1.690 \times \text{IS}) - (.220 \times \text{IT}) - (.573 \times \text{TM})$$

It can be stated that the independent variables OC and IS have a positive and statistically significant effect on dependent variable supply chain performance at the other hand the the variables IT and TM have negative and statistically significant impact to the predict dependent variable SCP, $p < .05$. However, the variables T did not have any significant influence in the dependent variable. SCP, $p < .786$.

Table 8
Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta				Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.196	.070		-2.796	.006		
	T	-.008	.028	-.007	-.271	.786	.282	3.552
	OC	.153	.031	.142	4.890	.000	.208	4.817
	IS	1.695	.041	1.478	41.195	.000	.137	7.318
	IT	-.220	.062	-.169	-3.521	.000	.076	13.147
	TM	-.574	.042	-.564	-13.543	.000	.102	9.845
2	(Constant)	-.198	.070		-2.846	.005		
	OC	.150	.029	.139	5.156	.000	.240	4.171
	IS	1.690	.036	1.474	46.764	.000	.177	5.661
	IT	-.220	.062	-.170	-3.529	.000	.076	13.145
	TM	-.573	.042	-.562	-13.649	.000	.103	9.672
a. Dependent Variable: SCP								

The following table displays the overall impact of all variable on the dependent variable in terms of their rejection and acceptance.

Table 9

Summary of Hypotheses

No.	Hypotheses	Sig value	Status
H ₁	There is no significant effect of trust in logistic collaboration on the performance of supply chain.	.786	Failed to reject
H ₂	There is no significant effect of organizational commitment in logistic collaboration on the performance of supply chain.	.000	Rejected
H ₃	There is no significant effect of interdependence of supply chain partners in logistic collaboration on the performance of supply chain.	.000	Rejected
H ₄	There is no significant effect of infrastructure and information technology in logistic collaboration on the performance of supply chain	.000	Rejected
H ₅	There is no significant effect of top managerial involvement management engagement in logistic collaboration on the performance of supply chain.	.000	Rejected

Conclusion

The results indicate supply chain collaboration as an effective method to improve supply chain performance. It also opens the door for further exploration regarding the factors associated with collaborative practices in supply chain management. The primary objective of the study was to identify the factors of supply chain collaboration that effect supply chain performance and to what extent these factors influence the performance of supply chain. The results reveals that the increased level of organizational commitment, interdependence in supply chain practices, information technology in supply chain, the development of infrastructure and involvement of top management significantly impacts supply chain performance. As Joshi (2011) describes that supply chain is largely based on the concept of successive dependence on activities. These activities must, therefore, be coordinated. The interdependence of is crucial for the effectiveness of each transaction in supply chain process, as this dependency is related to the use of resources. By using common resources, economies of scale can be achieved by implementing the individual activities of different supply chains. The results also support the idea from literature that logistics arise when the necessary resources are purchased jointly from two or more units, which require interconnections. Suppliers must seek to work with enterprises located in different parts of the globe and to focus on the general needs of the corporation and building connections.

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